

ArH) and 7.66 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, *p*-anisyl); d, 230–31°; e, 223–24°; f, 205–06°.

3-[4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1H, 5H-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]propanoic acid (8): A mixture of 4 (5 g, 25 mmol) and 3-aminopropanoic acid (2.6 g, 30 mmol) was heated at 160–65° for 1 h. The resulting solid was dissolved in aqueous NaHCO₃ and the solution was clarified by animal charcoal, filtered and acidified with HCl. The product was crystallised from H₂O-HOAc (10 : 90, v/v), (4.98 g, 69%), m.p. 194–95°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 950 (OH), 1 730 and 1 680 (CO) and 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

8-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H,6H-pyrido[2,1-b](1,3)oxazin-2,6-dione (12): Compound 8 (8 g) was refluxed with Ac₂O (5 ml) and the solution was cooled and filtered. The resulting solid was washed with aqueous NaHCO₃ and water, and crystallised from H₂O-HOAc (10 : 90, v/v), (4.28 g, 93%), m.p. 185–86° (Found: C, 66.32; H, 4.86; N, 5.14. C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₄ calcd. for: C, 66.41; H, 4.82; N, 5.16%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 800 (lactone CO), 1 670 (pyridone CO), 1 600 (C=C) and 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 3.0 (2H, t, J 5 Hz, N-CH₂), 4.43 (2H, t, J 5 Hz, OCH₃), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.26 (1H, d, H-9, $J_{o-\tau}$ 2 Hz), 6.63 (1H, H-7, $J_{\tau-\rho}$ 2 Hz), 7.0 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl) and 7.56 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl).

(4-Aryl-1-piperazinyl)amides of 3-[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1H,5H-pyridin-2,6-dion-1-yl]propanoic acid (15): A mixture of 12 (37 mmol) and 1-aryl-piperazine (50 mmol) was refluxed in acetone (10 ml) for 2 h. The solution was then concentra-

ted and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture (80 : 20, v/v): 5a, m.p. 211–12°; b, 222–23°; c, 200–01°; d, 216–17°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 710 and 1 670 (imide CO), 1 630 (amide CO) and 1 240 cm⁻¹ (C–O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.29 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.7 (2H, t, J_{vis} 9 Hz, N-CH₂), 3.14 (4H, m, Ar-N(CH₂)₂), 3.66 (4H, m, CON(CH₂)₂), 3.8 (2H, s, =C-CH₂CO), 3.88 (³H, s, OCH₃), 4.26 (2H, t, J_{vis} 9 Hz, COCH₂), 6.95, (2H, d, J_o 8 Hz, *p*-tolyl), 7.1 (2H, d, J_o 8 Hz, *p*-tolyl), 6.86 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl) and 7.54 (2H, d, J_o 9 Hz, *p*-anisyl); e, 209–10°; f, 195–96°; g, 165–66°.

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Synthesis of some New Benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyridazin-3(1*H*)-ones and Benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-3-ones

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The benzofuran derivatives have exhibited various biological activities¹. The esterogenic activity of some furocoumarins has been extensively recorded². Recently, the synthesis of new benzofuranopyrazoles and benzofuranopyrimidines have been recorded^{3,4}. We report herein some new benzofuranopyridazinones and benzofuranopyrazoles.

Results and Discussion

Thymoxyacetic acid was prepared by thereaction of thymol with chloroacetic acid in presence of alkali⁵ which on bromination gave 4-bromothymoxyacetic acid. Thymoxyacetic acid and 4-bromothy-

moxycetic acid on polyphosphoric acid cyclisation gave the benzofurone 2 and 2' respectively. Their formation was evidenced by disappearance of acidic-OH encountered at δ 14.5 in the pmr spectra and broad ir band at 3 100–3 400 cm⁻¹. The conversion of compound 2 to 3 and 2' to 3' was confirmed by the appearance of ester carbonyl and furocarbonyl ir bands around 1 740 and 1 720 cm⁻¹ respectively. The formation of the substituted benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyridazin-3(1*H*)-ones (4 and 4') from the esters (3 and 3') respectively and substituted arylhydrazides was confirmed by disappearance of the furocarbonyl and ester carbonyl and the appearance of the amido carbonyl around 1 680 cm⁻¹ in

the ir spectra of 4 and 4'. The formation of the substituted-benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-3(1*H*)-ones (6) from the ester (5) and substituted arylhydrazides was confirmed by disappearance of the furocar-

bonyl and ester carbonyl and appearance of the amido carbonyl at 1 680 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra. The structures of all the compounds have been supported by spectral analysis.

4a, 4'a, 6a : R = *m*-CH₃.C₆H₄OCH₂
 4b, 4'b, 6b : R = *p*-CH₃.C₆H₄OCH₂
 4c, 4'c, 6c : R = 3-CH₃-4-Cl.C₆H₃OCH₂
 4d, 4'd, 6d : R = *p*-NO₂.C₆H₄OCH₂
 4e, 4'e, 6e : R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄OCH₂
 4f, 4'f, 6f : R = 3,5-(NO₂)₂.C₆H₃
 4g, 4'g, 6g : R = *p*-Cl.C₆H₄OCH.CH₃
 4h, 4'h, 6h : R = 2-OH-5-Cl.C₆H₃
 4i, 4'i : R = 2,4-(CH₃)₂.C₆H₃OCH.CH₃
 4j, 4'j : R = *o*-CH₃.C₆H₄OCH.CH₃

4k, 4'k : R = *m*-CH₃.C₆H₄OCH-CH₃
 4l, 6l : R = *o*-NO₂.C₆H₄OCH₂
 4m : R = 3-CH₃-4-Cl.C₆H₃OCH.CH₃
 4n : R = *o*-CH₃.C₆H₄OCH₂
 4o : R = 2,4-(Cl)₂.C₆H₃OCH₂
 4p : R = C₆H₅OCH.CH₃
 4q : R = C₆H₅OCH₂
 4r : R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄
 4'l, 6j : R = 2(CH₃)₂CH.5-CH₃.C₆H₃OCH₂
 6k : R = C₆H₅-CH₂

Comps. 4'a-1 and 6a-k are 8- and 7-bromosubstituted derivatives respectively.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-237 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3/TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G.

Thymoxyacetic acid was prepared from thymol and chloroacetic acid by a known method⁵ which on bromination gave 4-bromothymoxyacetic acid. Similarly, 4-methyl-7-isopropylbenzofuran-3(2H)-one (2) was prepared by the reported method^{4,5}.

4-Methyl-5-bromo-7-isopropyl benzofuran-3(2H)-one (2'): A mixture of 4-bromothymoxyacetic acid (0.03 mol) in polyphosphoric acid (15 ml) and P_2O_5 (8 g) was stirred for 30 min and heated further gently on a water-bath at 80° for about 2 h, then cooled and poured in ice-water (200 ml). The resulting solid was washed with sodium bicarbonate and recrystallised from alcohol, (58%), m.p. 77° (Found: C, 53.51; H, 4.80. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 53.53; H, 4.83%); ν_{max} 1 720 (cyclic C=O), 1 600 (C=C) and 1 035–1 050 cm^{-1} (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.18 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8 (1H, s, C_6 -ArH).

4-Methyl-7-isopropyl-2,3-dihydro-3-oxo-benzofuro-2-ethylacetate (3): To a mixture of 2 (0.025 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.05 mol) in acetone (40 ml), K_2CO_3 (5 g) was added and the mixture refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (58%), m.p. 103° (Found: C, 69.51; H, 7.23. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 69.56; H, 7.24%); ν_{max} 1 740 (ester C=O), 1 720 (cyclic C=O), 1 580–1 600 (C=C) and 1 035–1 060 cm^{-1} (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.3 (3H, t, J 8.5 Hz, CH_3 ester), 2.3 (3H, s, C_4 - ArCH_3), 2.6 (2H, d, CH_2CO), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.2 (2H, q, J 8.5, OCH_2 ester), 4.6 (1H, t, OCH) and 6.8–6.9 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, ArH).

4-Methyl-5-bromo-7-isopropyl-2,3-dihydro-3-oxo-benzofuro-2-ethylacetate (3'): To a mixture of 2' (0.025 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.05 mol) in acetone (40 ml), K_2CO_3 (5 g) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 83° (Found: C, 54.00; H, 5.30. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 54.08; H, 5.53%); ν_{max} 1 740 (ester C=O), 1 720 (cyclic C=O), 1 600 (C=C) and 1 060 cm^{-1} (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.3 (3H, t, J 8.5 Hz, CH_3 ester), 2.3 (3H, s, C_4 - ArCH_3), 2.6 (2H, d, CH_2CO), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.15 (2H, q, J 8.5 Hz, OCH_2 ester), 4.65 (1H, t, OCH) and 6.8 (1H, s, C_6 -ArH).

2-Aroyl-6-isopropyl-9-methylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyridazin-3(1H)-one (4a): To a solution 3 (0.005 mol) in methanol (25 ml), *m*-methylphenoxyacetic

acid hydrazide (0.005 mol) was added and the mixture refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath and then the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The separated solid was crystallised from methanol, (49%), m.p. 98° (Found: C, 70.36; H, 6.10; N, 7.12. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 70.40; H, 6.12; N, 7.14%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 250 (NH), 1 670 (broad -CON-) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 2.3 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_3$), 2.45 (2H, s, OCH_2), 3.2, (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8–7.3 (6H, m, ArH). Similarly other pyridazinones (yields 51–85%) were prepared: 4b, m.p. 128°; c, 167°; d, 135°; e, 194°; f, 117°; g, 127°; h, 133°; i, 110°; j, 82°; k, 93°; l, 76°; m, 125°; n, 59°; o, 53°; p, 72°; q, 216°; r, 71°.

2-Aroyl-6-isopropyl-8-bromo-9-methylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyridazin-3(1H)-one (4'a): To a solution of 3' (0.005 mol) in methanol (25 ml), *m*-methylphenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (0.0005 mol) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the separated solid was crystallised from methanol, (50%), m.p. 91° (Found: C, 58.51; H, 4.80; N, 5.91. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 58.59; H, 4.88; N, 5.94%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 200 (NH), 1 680 (-CON-) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.3 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_3$), 2.45 (2H, s, COCH_2), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8–7.3 (5H, m, ArH). Similarly other pyridazinones (yields 48–77%) were prepared: 4'b, m.p. 76°; c, 141°; d, 104°; e, 153°; f, 156°; g, 36°; h, 213°; i, 114°; j, 107°; k, 83°; l, 118°.

4-Methyl-5-bromo-7-isopropyl-3-oxobenzofuro-2-ethylcarboxylate (5): To a mixture of (2') (0.025 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (0.05 mol) in acetone (40 ml), K_2CO_3 (5 g) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The solid formed was crystallised from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 97° (Found: C, 52.70; H, 4.91. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 52.78, H, 4.98%); ν_{max} 1 740 (ester C=O), 1 720 (cyclic C=O), 1 580–1 600 (C=C) and 1 085–1 060 cm^{-1} (-O-); δ 1.1 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.3 (3H, t, J 8.5 Hz, ester CH_3), 2.3 (3H, s, C_4 - ArCH_3), 3.2 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.2 (2H, q, J 8.5 Hz, OCH_2 -ester), 4.6 (1H, s, -OCH-) and 6.8–6.9 (1H, s, J 8 Hz, ArH).

2-Aroyl-5-isopropyl-7-bromo-8-methylbenzofuro[2,3-c]pyrazol-3-(1H)-one (6a): To a solution of 5 (0.003 mol) in methanol (25 ml), *m*-methylphenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (0.0003 mol) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the solid separated was crystallised from methanol, (59%), m.p. 93° (Found: C, 57.61; H 4.51; N, 6.09. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4\text{H}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 57.76; H, 4.59; N, 6.12%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 250 (NH), 1 690–1 600 (C=O) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.1 (6H, d, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 2.3 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{ArCH}_3$), 3.2 (1H, m, CH), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH_2) and 6.8–7.3 (5H, m, ArH) Similarly